

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE & ARTS

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Tomillus et guarnieri.

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Cover: graphic reworking of image number 2 of Leena Löfstedt's article, courtesy of Dr. Elizabeth Morrison, Senior Curator of Manuscripts, J. Paul Getty Museum, Los Angeles (manuscript Ludwig XIV.2).

The marginal note states *Nota illud esse guarnerii* 'NB That belongs to Garnier'. The adjacent text Decr. C 10 q 2 c 2 § 11 reads *Si yconomus ecclesiae*

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE AND ARTS

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